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Engineering Education for Sustainable Cities in Africa:

Conversations from Kenya

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ABSTRACT

Projected urban growth in Kenya will require increased engineering talent and resources to facilitate the infrastructure demands of growing urban centers [1]. This study aims to understand how Kenyan institutions are currently equipped to support engineering programs and what factors need to be considered to reform the curricula to support rapid urban growth in the region. To investigate these questions, a research team travelled to Kenya in July, 2016 to study the engineering programs and interview faculty members at two universities. The method of currere was used as a framework for analyzing the regressive, the progressive, the analytical and the synthetical. Four key insights emerged from the study: opportunities exist for curriculum reform of Kenyan engineering curricula to mirror emerging engineering pedagogy and practice, context is a critical factor in curriculum reform, accreditation is a key consideration for online learning in engineering education, and there was an openness to collaboration regarding curriculum reform. This study focused on the perspective of the educational institution. As such, further research is suggested regarding the institutional factors, notably the accreditation standards for online learning, the industry objectives and the policy objectives to inform the context of the conversations of engineering education in Kenya.

Conference Key Areas: Sustainability and Engineering Education, Open and Online Engineering Education, Curriculum Development

Keywords: Engineering Education, Online Learning, Curriculum Reform, Accreditation

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INTRODUCTION

Kenya is experiencing significant urban population growth [2]. In order to accommodate this growth, there is a substantial need for additional engineering talent and resources to design, build and manage new and sustainable city infrastructure. A large component of this capacity building will be achieved through the education and training of engineers who can use sustainable approaches to build and maintain new infrastructure [1].

Researchers from the University of Toronto recently met with faculty members in engineering at two large public universities in Kenya. Their visit was part of a larger project that is exploring a curriculum for engineering education for sustainable cities in Africa. The goals of this particular study were to build on the literature surrounding engineering education in Kenya, discover how the country is prepared to manage current and future urban growth rates through engineering education, and explore the potential of developing an online engineering education curriculum that is accessible and locally contextualized to promote the sustainable development of growing urban centers. The findings from the study will set the stage for deeper study in to the larger research.

The method of currere [3] was used to explore the conversations regarding engineering curricula, those involved in the conversations and the surrounding contexts in Kenya. The method of currere encourages researchers to analyze their own experiences in relation to the cultural, historical and political contexts of education to understand more fully, with more complexity and subtlety, the current realities [4]. This is accomplished through consideration of the regressive, the progressive, the analytical and the synthetical aspects [3].

Both researchers felt it was important to discuss the intent of the project due to the prospect of interfering as opposed to supporting, as other prior interventions were criticized of being neoliberal in nature. Extensive and proper consideration was taken when framing the following research questions:

1. How are institutions currently equipped to support engineering education in Kenya?
2. What factors need to be considered to reform the engineering curricula to support rapid urban growth in Kenya?
3. What lessons can we learn from conversations with universities in Kenya?

1 LITERATURE REVIEW

Engineering education was introduced in Eastern Africa in 1956 as part of the University of East Africa, which separated into three distinct universities in 1970: one in Kenya, Tanzania and Uganda. The presence of accredited engineering programs has since expanded to nine universities in Kenya recognized under the Engineers Board of Kenya (EBK) accreditation body.

Amutabi (2003) and Case et. al (2016) note that politics play an important role in the development of society as they impact the structures of modern societies [5], [6]. Gaining its independence from England in 1963, the political climate in Kenya had a significant impact on the development of the country's education system [6]. The country experienced a period of politically motivated, rapid expansion in universities during the 1980s [5]. Universities were overloaded as their infrastructures and resources were not equipped to handle such a large number of students. This was

especially challenging for engineering programs which require a balance of theoretical, practical and experiential learning [7], often requiring many resources outside of the classroom, including laboratory space and equipment, in addition to the human capacity required to facilitate this learning.

The emphasis on financial investment in tertiary education was later diverted to elementary and secondary education [6]. As a result, universities removed tutorial sessions - an important part of engineering education - to deal with the problem of underfunded and understaffed faculty. Tutorial sessions provided opportunities for students to participate in discussion: an important part of student curricula due to the importance of reflection in learning [8].

Acknowledging the historical context that shaped the engineering programs in Kenya, this research study aimed to understand the current state of the engineering programs, how they were influenced by this historical context and how the engineering curricula may reform in the wake of engineering education research and evolving societal needs.

Curriculum reform is a popular topic in engineering education literature as engineering education and the training of engineers are considered key to the progression of the economy [6]. Kenya's rapid urban growth brings to light two pressing questions regarding curriculum reform: how can the engineering curriculum evolve to incorporate emerging knowledge regarding sustainable urban development?; and, how can engineering curriculum be scaled to build the engineering capacity required to tackle the growing infrastructure demands expected to emerge as the cities continue to grow?

With the increase in popularity around online education, specifically in engineering related courses, there is a growing opportunity to share educational resources internationally and to seek ways in leveraging the benefits in a Kenyan context. Online learning is viewed as a way to increase access to education to students who cannot afford the cost of tuition, and decrease the commuting volume of students who are already registered.

As an attempt to capitalize on this potential, the World Bank introduced the African Virtual University (AVU) project in 1998 [9]. The goal of the project was to support what it viewed as failing higher education in Sub-Saharan Africa by introducing high quality education to Kenya through modern information technology systems. The hope was to educate individuals through distance education and increase the number of well-trained African scientists, technicians, engineers and business managers required for economic development [9]. However, the World Bank's association with the AVU project was viewed by some as a source of neoliberal policy models imposed on developing countries. Despite the intent of offering courses focused on engineering, a search for engineering courses on the AVU website yields no results.

The literature on engineering education in Kenya paints an incomplete picture of the country's ability to deliver to the discipline in an online setting. Studies of the status of engineering education in Kenya were few and far between. Based on their impressions and experiences in engineering and education research, the researchers felt that such little information available presented a need to study the institutions more closely and in person.

2 METHODS

This study into engineering education in Kenya used data collected from a larger

project for the development of engineering education for sustainable cities in Africa. The project collected data from a variety of educational and cultural contexts that included engineering education at universities in Africa. Interview data relevant to the Kenyan context were selected from the larger project.

2.1 Participants

Ten faculty members from two public Kenyan universities were interviewed for this study. Participants were chosen based on their experience in engineering education and their availability during the visit. For each case, participants underwent a formal consent process prior to their involvement. This process followed the ethics procedures of the University of Toronto. The identities of both universities have been anonymized to KU1 and KU2 (i.e. Kenyan University 1 and Kenyan University 2). The identities of the participants have been anonymized to participant 1, 2, etc. Participants 1 to 4 were from KU1 and participants 5 to 8 were from KU2.

2.2 Data Collection

A semi-structured group interview was conducted at each university, recorded, and then transcribed. Interviews lasted 60 to 90 minutes. Interview questions were structured around seven themes: cities and urbanization, engineering education, online and distance learning, scalability, sustainability, virtual labs, and engineering employment. Group interviews were used to explore contemporary engineering-education contexts in East Africa, survey engineering-education approaches including online learning strategies and methods, and integrate knowledge gained to devise highly scalable engineering education approaches suitable to resource-constrained settings. All interviews were contextualized by individuals' learning and cultural contexts. Field notes were also taken as part of the data collection.

2.3 Data Analysis

Using the currere method [8], data from conversations related to engineering education were extracted from the interview transcripts. Both researchers analyzed both sets of the transcripts. They then reviewed and discussed relevant information. An inductive approach led to the extraction of relevant information and avoided the biasing of the results [10]. Selected information emerged from the phrases that revealed details related to devise highly scalable engineering education approaches suitable to resource-constrained settings. The identified details were then triangulated across locations and participant roles. The combination of the two data sources facilitated a deeper understanding of engineering education in Kenyan universities.

3 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

A strength of the method of currere originates from framing the curriculum as a conversation or a series of conversations [4]. The interview questions elicited several conversations surrounding the state of engineering education in Kenya. The content of the conversations varied from one university to another, however, the topics below were present in each interview.

3.1 Opportunity for Curriculum Reform

The opportunity for curriculum reform emerged throughout the interviews. Participants acknowledged that there is a need to revisit traditional approaches to engineering education from a pedagogical and content perspective to keep up to date with emerging technologies and advances in engineering pedagogy and practice.

It was noted that the undergraduate curriculum had not been extensively updated from the initial curriculum developed in the 1960's (KU1) which was created under British influence. Topics that have since gained attention, such as sustainability, have not been explicitly incorporated into the curricula. The universities "teach the hard engineering" (participant 1), focused on theory, and acknowledge that "the curriculum is long due for review" (participant 1). Faculty, however, did not see this as an independently driven initiative, suggesting that "[we] need the innovation, the outreach, [and] the new ideas from the developed world institutions... [such as] America, Britain, [and] Canada" (participant 2).

These institutions have content connected to emerging practice in engineering. However, the inclusion of these topics is generally limited to graduate degrees, such as programs dedicated to climate change and hydrology, and are not formally a part of the undergraduate curriculum. Informal inclusion of emerging topics in engineering in the undergraduate curriculum stem from individual instructors who choose to adapt their course curricula to include topics of interest (KU1).

In addition to the potential for updating content, participants discussed the opportunity for reform of the pedagogical approach to their engineering programs. In the current structure, the universities provide the theory in the classroom and the graduates need to gain exposure to the field outside of their studies. This may come in the form of practical attachments, where students have the opportunity to work in industry throughout or following their studies, or through other experiences sought after by the student (KU1 and KU2). The challenges with incorporating these practical experiences into the curriculum come from limited resources. As one participant stated, "it's difficult to [increase the practical component] in the university with the number [of students], with minimal finances [and] with minimal equipment" (participant 5).

Further, the demand for these programs, notably civil engineering, far exceeds the capacity of the program to accept the students, noted by one participant "we find that many students would like to come to civil engineering ... but we don't have the capacity to absorb them all" (participant 3).

These issues produced conversations about the need for several changes including classroom setup, delivery method and curriculum design that may allow for a shift in the teaching approach and the increase in program capacity. Through these conversations, the opportunities for emerging technology in engineering education came to light allowing us to explore whether there are ways that online resources could be used to assist with the pedagogical shift facing the engineering programs and the apparent limited capacity for growth.

3.2 Importance of Context in Curriculum Reform

Context emerged as a key factor in the conversations regarding curriculum reform as it impacts both curriculum content and engineering pedagogy.

In the case of urban infrastructure, participants noted the disparity in urban development between developed and developing countries:

In the context of our cities, I would say it is a little bit different than developed countries where the government puts infrastructure first and then people second. Here we settle first. Then people come ... then infrastructure comes. So, we develop from our village then to a town then to a city. And in that transition, the key challenges will be socio[technical]. (participant 3)

These types of localized differences with regards to urban development would lend themselves to different course content: different case studies, different approaches to design, or use of different technologies. As such, content developed for the Canadian context would not necessarily be relevant for the Kenyan context.

The political and institutional contexts were noted as a factor in curriculum reform with regards to pedagogy and content. Participant 4 described their lack of autonomy in curriculum development as follows:

The main stumbling block has been the accreditation body. They tend to be quite traditional and, I think, in the future as those members are phased out, we will be able to offer some of this new program because some of these sustainable concepts, I think, they cannot wrap their minds around it.

This contradicted another participant who indicated that the “accreditation does not get involved in the material. They look at the curriculum and how we deliver. They really don't get involved” (participant 6).

This localized context can play a significant role in the development of curriculum, where one institution feels stifled by the accreditation body and another institution feels like they have autonomy in their curriculum development. In this case, one solution that may be appropriate for one institution may not be appropriate for the other. The accreditation factor is further explored in the subsequent section as it plays a role in the considerations for online learning.

These findings were consistent with a research study that focused on the significance of context for curriculum development in engineering education in Kenya, Tanzania and South Africa. This study highlighted the importance in considering context in curriculum design, finding that historical context, political objectives, industry objectives and institutional objectives influence curriculum reform through accreditation and funding, availability of resources, expectations of graduates and departmental autonomy [6]. Without an understanding and consideration of context, interventions are at risk of being less effective.

3.3 Accreditation Considerations for Online Learning

Accreditation emerged as another topic conversation in the design and development of online learning material. Differing opinions between universities arose during the conversations of online learning implementation. Participant 3 from KU1 stated:

We cannot replace the existing [curriculum] because EBK has an issue especially for undergraduate. So, the only thing that can be done is, as he said, when we look at the soft or easy options [for online learning]. First engineers who are in the field we upgrade them to online. At the same time, there are those who want to do their masters where EBK does not play a role [in the curriculum]... But then later on when maybe EBK [becomes] a bit more understanding then [online learning] can be scaled down to bachelors.

This excerpt demonstrates barriers to the introduction of online learning in undergraduate engineering courses and suggests using online learning in graduate courses first. Participant 4 from KU1 further added to the accreditation barrier of implementing online engineering courses at the bachelor level.

So, that has been a challenge in terms of incorporating teaching the open [online] learning. I think some courses can be replaced such that you have distance learners using technology, video conferencing satellite and so on. But

these are concepts that the [EBK] currently, as constituted, cannot accept. So, as those members are phased out and we bring in you guys with fresh ideas, we will be able to catch up with the rest of the world.

A different response was provided regarding involvement of the accreditation body during our conversation with the participants from KU2. One of the researchers asked if the accreditation board limited what they could put online as far as course material. Participant 7 responded, “no.” Participant 6 added that “accreditation does not get involved in the material. They look at the curriculum and how we deliver. They really don't get involved.” The conversation progressed to a discussion around the implementation and evaluation of their online courses.

We have caught areas where we are able to have parallel groups. Group going through conventional way purely another one going through blended mode purely, but they take the same examination and then you check: is this mechanism or the style of delivery mode capable of teaching? And we have proved that the distance education is capable of teaching just as well as the conventional teaching. So, the end product is one way of judging and so on. (participant 8)

These differing responses provide direction for further exploration into the standards for online learning set by the accrediting body, EBK. It is not clear why participants 6 and 7 responded to the question with optimistic certainty while participant 4 professed a lack of optimism and the presentation of a barrier by the same accrediting body. It was disclosed to us during our visit to Kenya that the accrediting board was made up of members primarily from a single university. If this is true, it may begin to explain a difference in comfort with new ways of teaching at the different institutions, and expand the scope of the research to include the role of the accreditation board.

3.4 Openness to Collaborate

Ensuring that the project team was pursuing the study ethically with the universities in Kenya was an important aspect stated at the beginning of the paper. The researchers did not want to be perceived as interfering in their affairs or imposing their own doctrine. Fortunately, participant feedback from both universities validated our inquiry into engineering education in Kenya. A sentiment shared by participant 8 when they expressed an openness and desire to collaborate:

[We] are generally ready to collaborate in this process in seeing how it can translate into some tangible things later on when the research part of it is completed and recommendations and suggestions started.

This sentiment affirmed our belief in a beneficial outcome of our team's presence in the region and undertaking of the study. A senior administrator also made an appearance while we were conducting our interviews. They expressed an interest in signing a memorandum of understanding for further collaboration between our universities on this matter. This confirmed an openness and desire for collaboration between the research team and both universities in Kenya.

4 CONCLUSION

Using the method of currere framed under the three research questions, four key insights emerged from this study:

1. Opportunities exist for curriculum reform of Kenyan engineering curricula to

- mirror emerging engineering pedagogy and practice;
2. Context is a critical factor in curriculum reform, especially when considering inter-institutional or international collaboration of developing learning resources;
 3. Accreditation is a key consideration for online learning in engineering education; and,
 4. There exists an openness to collaboration regarding curriculum reform.

Fig 1. Progression of four key insights.

Although there is opportunity for reform, challenges for addressing the growing need for engineers in Kenya emerged throughout the research study. Limited institutional capacity, including physical, human and technological capacity, limited funding, and unclear curriculum accreditation standards all present challenges for the scalability of the engineering programs. These findings, coupled with an openness from both universities to collaborate, present an opportunity to explore online and distance learning initiatives that have the potential to address both pedagogical challenges, as well as curriculum content challenges.

The findings from this study may be used to inform design and collaboration considerations of the larger research project, or any other similar undertaking in the region. As context emerged as a critical factor in curriculum reform, more research is suggested regarding the institutional factors, notably the accreditation standards for online learning, the industry objectives and the policy objectives to inform the context of the conversations of engineering education in Kenya.

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